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Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) Complexes with 3(2'-furoyl) 2-Cyano Ethyl Crotonate

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IN the programme of preparing complexes of rare and higher co-ordination numbers with divalent first transition series metal ions, polydentate chelating ligands are being synthesised since such ligands dominate the area of higher co-ordination polyhedra in scope, numbers and also from kinetic and thermodynamic stability point of view. Particularly, the compact nature of polydentate schiff's bases make them more effective in attaining high co-ordination structure. Earlier complexation behaviour of bi, tri and tetradentate schiff's bases have been reported¹⁻⁵. In this communication a number of Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and

Zn(II) complexes with a bidentate ligand derived from condensation of furfuraldehyde and ethyl cyanoacetate will be presented.

Experimental

Synthesis of the Ligands: Furfuraldehyde and ethyl cyanoacetate in 1:1 proportion were mixed with 1 cc of piperidine as base and refluxed for 6-8 hours. The contents were poured into a 10% solution of hydrochloric acid and kept standing for six days. Pinkish-violet crystalline compound separated out which was filtered, washed with ether and dried in vacuum.

Preparation of Complexes: Ethanolic solution of different metal salts were treated with ethanolic solution of the ligand in 1:2 proportion and the resulting solution refluxed for one hour. On keeping the resulting solution overnight crystalline compounds separated. These were filtered under suction, washed with ethanol and ether and dried in vacuum desiccator.

Metal and nitrogen in the complexes were estimated by standard methods. Conductance was measured in M/1000 acetone solution using Toshniwal conductivity bridge. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made on solid specimens at room temperature by the Guoy method. I. R. spectra were recorded using Perkin-Elmer-337 and Beckman I. R.-12 spectrophotometers. Electronic spectra were recorded on a Hilger-watt uvispeck spectrophotometer with M/100 chloroform solution of the complexes. Analytical, conductance, magnetic susceptibility and spectral data are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compounds	M. P. (°C)	Λ_M (mhos. cm ²)	μ_{eff} (B. M.)	% metal		% nitrogen		Electronic spectra ν_{max} in k. k. (ϵ)
				Found.	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	
CoCl ₂ L ₂	165	6.5	4.9	11.25	11.51	5.22	5.47	18.8 (35), 8.0 (16)
CoBr ₂ L ₂	185	7.3	5.0	9.48	9.82	4.25	4.66	19.2 (38), 8.0 (16)
Co(NO ₃) ₂ L ₂	180	6.8	5.2	10.15	10.43	9.58	9.91	19.4 (40), 8.2 (18)
NiCl ₂ L	202	7.4	—	18.11	18.30	4.02	4.36	16.5 (50)
NiBr ₂ L	198	8.2	—	14.15	14.37	3.05	3.42	17.4 (54)
Ni(NO ₃) ₂ L	176	8.5	—	15.46	15.71	10.91	11.24	18.0 (55)
CuCl ₂ L ₂	205	5.8	1.78	12.05	12.30	5.22	5.42	14.8 (30)
CuBr ₂ L ₂	196	6.2	1.80	10.21	10.51	4.31	4.63	15.0 (35)
Cu(NO ₃) ₂ L ₂	190	6.5	1.82	10.85	11.15	9.56	9.83	15.3 (40)
ZnCl ₂ L ₂	185	8.2	—	12.26	12.61	5.20	5.40	—
ZnBr ₂ L ₂	176	8.4	—	10.45	10.78	4.28	4.62	—
Zn(NO ₃) ₂ L ₂	183	7.5	—	11.21	11.44	9.56	9.80	—

L=3 (2'-Furoyl)-2-cyano ethyl crotonate.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes have the general formula ML_2X_2 where $M = Co(II), Cu(II), Zn(II)$, $X = Cl^-, Br^-, NO_3^-$ and $L = 3(2\text{'-furoyl})\text{-2-cyano ethyl crotonate}$, excepting the nickel complexes which have the composition MLX_2 . Cobalt complexes are pink, nickel complexes red, copper complexes green in colour and zinc complexes are white. They have relatively low melting points and are soluble in acetone in which medium the low molar conductance values (Table 1) indicate them to be non-electrolytes. Magnetic moment of cobalt complexes are in the range of 4.9-5.2 B.M. suggesting a spin free octahedral configuration. Nickel complexes are diamagnetic and copper complexes have moments in the range of 1.78-1.82 B.M. as expected for the presence of a single unpaired electron.

In the infrared spectra of the ligand $\nu(C=O)$ appears⁶ at 1690, $\nu(C=C)$ at 1620 and $\nu(C\equiv N)$ at 2220 cm^{-1} . On the complexation of the ligand, in the metal complexes $\nu(C=O)$ is observed $\sim 1590 - 1600 cm^{-1}$ region, where as the absorption due to $\nu(C\equiv N)$ disappears and a new band is observed around 1490 cm^{-1} which can be assigned as $\nu(C=N)$. Hence the ligand coordinates through the oxygen of the $(C=O)$ groups and nitrogen of the nitrile group. This has been further substantiated by observation⁷ of $\nu(M-O)$ and $\nu(M-N)$ $\sim 420 - 450$ and $250 - 280 cm^{-1}$ region respectively. In the spectra of nitrate complexes the difference ($\nabla\nu$) between the position of ν_4 and ν_1 band is $\sim 130 cm^{-1}$ which indicates⁸⁻¹⁰ the presence of unidentate nitrate group.

In the electronic spectra of $Co(II)$ complexes two absorption bands were observed $\sim 18.8 - 19.4$ (35 - 40) and 8.0 - 8.2 (16 - 18) k. k. regions assignable¹¹ to $4T_{1g} \rightarrow 4T_{1g}$ (P) and $4T_{1g} \rightarrow 4T_{2g}$ (F) transitions respectively. On the basis of the position of absorption bands and magnetic moment data a spin-free octahedral configuration is expected for these complexes. All the diamagnetic nickel (II) complexes show one broad absorption band $\sim 16 - 18$ (50 - 55) k. k. regions, which suggests^{12,13} a possible square planar configuration for these complexes. Copper (II) complexes give rise to one broad absorption band $\sim 14 - 15.3$ (30 - 40) k. k. regions indicating presumably a distorted octahedral configuration. Even though at least three transitions are expected^{14,15} in this case, all the three are very close in energy and often give rise to a single broad band envelope. On the basis of analysis, conductance and infrared spectral data, all the zinc complexes have an octahedral environment around the metal ion.

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Mono-organotin (IV) Derivatives of Hydroxamic Acids

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ORGANOTIN (IV) derivatives of hydroxamic acids have aroused considerable interest recently¹⁻⁴. However, except a few phenyltin derivatives of N-phenylbenzhydroxamic acid⁵, the chemistry of mono-organotin (IV) hydroxamates still remains unexplored. In the present paper we have described the synthetic and some structural aspects of some five-, six- and seven-coordinate mono-organotin (IV) compounds derived from hydroxamic acids.

Experimental

Reagents :

Hydroxamic acids were prepared by the literature procedure^{6,7}. Butyltin sesquioxide was purchased from T.N.O. Phenyltin trichloride and phenylstannic acid were prepared by the reported methods⁸. Phenyltin triisopropoxide was prepared by the reaction of sodium isopropoxide with phenyltintrichloride⁹. Benzene and tetrahydrofuran were dried over sodium wire.

General method of preparation of products (Table I) :

The reaction of organotin sesquioxide, $R_3SnO_{1.5}$, with hydroxamic acids, $RC(O)NR'OH$, (LH) in 1:1, 1:2

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